

"Empowering LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs isn't just about inclusivity—it's about unlocking innovation and resilience for a stronger economy. When investors and policymakers support diversity, we all thrive."

Ilustración 1 Diversity and entrepreneurship

Why Investing in LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurs Builds a Stronger, More Inclusive Economy

María Dolores González-Barbado

^a*Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Barcelona, Catalunya-Spain;*
*Phd Candidate -**

(a)mgonzalezbarbado@uoc.edu *

(a) ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4213-2090>

@lolagonzalezbarbado/ [Lola González Barbado | LinkedIn](#)

Abstract:

Investing in LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs is a powerful strategy for building a resilient and inclusive economy. Despite facing unique barriers rooted in identity and access, LGBTQ+ founders contribute innovation and diversity, driving progress across industries. This article explores how intentional support from investors and policymakers, alongside inclusive platforms like trade exhibitions, creates essential pathways for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs to thrive. Drawing on recent studies, we examine the impact of identity intersections on entrepreneurial journeys and highlight the transformative potential of diverse, empowered business ecosystems. Supporting LGBTQ+ entrepreneurship isn't just a commitment to equity—it's an investment in our shared economic future.

Keywords:

LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurship, Inclusive Economy, Diversity Investment, Trade Exhibitions, Economic Resilience, Entrepreneurial Identity, Policy Support, Intersectionality, Business Innovation, LGBTQ+ Founders

In today's market, the call for supporting LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs has become increasingly urgent, not just as a matter of social equity but as a strategic investment in economic innovation and diversity. Til Klein's work as a diversity investor has brought to light how critical support from investors and policymakers is for LGBTQ+ founders, whose entrepreneurial journeys are often hampered by unique structural and financial barriers (Klein, 2023a). This call to action is backed by research that highlights both the economic potential of LGBTQ+ businesses and the urgent need for systemic interventions to bridge gaps in funding, mentorship, and policy support (Fantappiè, 2022). Cha et al. (2019) argue that for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs, businesses can serve as a platform to challenge stereotypes and express authenticity. However, if the business suppresses their identity, it can lead to inner conflict and alienation. Entrepreneurs often face pressures to conform and may resort to emotional labor strategies to project a positive and resilient image despite discrimination.

Essers et al. (2023) highlight that LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs often navigate tensions between their personal identity and the external image of their business. In striving for entrepreneurial legitimacy, they may suppress aspects of their sexual identity to align with dominant capitalist and neoliberal narratives, which prioritize market strategy and business acumen over individual qualities and identity-driven values.

Why Investors Should Actively Support LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurs

Investors have a unique role in helping LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs overcome financial barriers, which often stem from systemic biases and a lack of visibility in traditional funding networks. For instance, LGBTQ+ founders frequently face exclusion from investment circles, not because of business viability, but due to perceptions that label them as high-risk, do the dominant discourse of entrepreneurship portrayed as a form of masculinity (Hamilton, 2013). Research indicates that targeted investment not only addresses this inequity but also opens new avenues for growth in sectors where LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs can leverage their unique insights and connections (Galloway, 2012).

Moreover, investors who prioritize diversity gain access to a largely untapped market with high consumer engagement potential. LGBTQ+-focused businesses are often community-centered and highly adaptable, aligning closely with consumer expectations for social responsibility, inclusion, and ethical business practices (Schindehutte et al., 2005). By actively seeking out and investing in LGBTQ+ ventures, investors can participate in building inclusive, future-ready industries while meeting a rising demand for diverse brands.

As Klein emphasized during his participation in the #WebSummit #Lisbon 2024, LGBTQ+ founders often bring an underrepresented but highly valuable perspective to their industries¹. They innovate by creating products and services tailored to niche communities, thereby fulfilling unmet consumer needs and driving growth in creative and digital sectors. From a strategic viewpoint, these investments are not only about social responsibility but also about recognizing and capturing the financial returns that diversity can yield (Maldonado-Bautista et al., 2023).

¹ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tilklein_lisbon-websummit-lgbtqfounders-activity-7262773574019465216-T4xo?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

The Policymaker's Role: Crafting an Inclusive and Equitable Business Environment

While investor support is critical, the policy landscape is equally influential in shaping the success of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs. Founders are frequently held back by limited access to capital, exclusion from business networks, and barriers in both private and public funding mechanisms. Here, policymakers can play a transformative role by introducing anti-discrimination policies that specifically target economic inclusion and establish equitable funding pathways (Washington et al., 2022).

For instance, establishing public funding initiatives and grants specifically for LGBTQ+ business ventures could help mitigate the funding gap. This approach has been demonstrated in countries like the Netherlands and Germany, where dedicated policies to support LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs have stimulated economic growth while promoting inclusivity (Yamamura et al., 2022) underscoring that well-designed policy frameworks not only enable LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs to thrive but also support a broader, more inclusive economic landscape.

Policies that promote visibility and inclusion can also drive systemic change by fostering entrepreneurial ecosystems where LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs feel empowered to pursue their ventures openly. This support may include initiatives like entrepreneurial hubs and incubators that provide networking opportunities, mentorship, and access to investors who are committed to diversity (Fletcher et al., 2024a). Additionally, regional support—such as local government grants or incentives to LGBTQ+-friendly business districts—can create safe and productive environments for these businesses to flourish, attracting both entrepreneurs and consumers from broader communities (Collins, 2004).

Building Collaborative Ecosystems: The Path Forward

The success of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs often hinges on collaborative support from both investors and policymakers who understand the value of diverse business ecosystems. Til Klein's efforts, alongside organizations like identity.vc, serve as powerful examples of how private investors and public sectors can work together to dismantle structural barriers (Fletcher et al., 2024b). Through tailored funding initiatives and supportive policies, these collaborations enable LGBTQ+ founders to bring their ideas to market while contributing to a dynamic and inclusive economy.

It is crucial for both investors and policymakers to recognize that supporting LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs is not merely a matter of ethics, but a powerful strategy for economic resilience. When diverse voices are empowered, they bring innovation and insight to industries often limited by conventional perspectives. A commitment to supporting LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs is a commitment to the future—one where economies thrive through diversity, resilience, and the inclusion of all voices (Kidney et al., 2024).

The Role of Identity and Intersectionality in LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurship

The unique challenges faced by LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs often intersect with identity-driven factors, which influence their experiences in both personal and professional domains. Earlier research, such as that by Chung (1995), revealed that LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs frequently encounter structural and social barriers—including workplace

discrimination, homophobia, and societal stigma—that shape their motivations and strategies for entering entrepreneurship. This idea of "push" and "pull" factors is explored further by Galloway (2007, 2011), who differentiates between the necessity-driven motivations (push factors) to escape workplace discrimination and the opportunity-driven motivations (pull factors) that allow LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs to serve niche markets and communities that mainstream businesses overlook. Such factors highlight that entrepreneurship is often a path for LGBTQ+ individuals to gain autonomy while fostering a safe, inclusive work environment for themselves and their communities.

Recent studies have emphasized that LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs navigate complex intersections of identity, notably shaped by heteronormativity and gender expectations. As Rumens and Ozturk (2019) argue, heteronormative structures in business reinforce the traditional image of the entrepreneur as heterosexual and male, creating an exclusionary framework that can limit LGBTQ+ representation and opportunity within mainstream entrepreneurship. Similarly, Wilson's study on a woman-led tech startup demonstrates how queer-inclusive spaces challenge conventional corporate norms, enabling LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs to build businesses that embrace values like empathy, collaboration, and communal support. These inclusive cultures stand in contrast to competitive, hierarchically structured workplaces and represent a model that is particularly supportive for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs and employees, who may feel marginalized in traditional settings (Klein, 2023b).

Furthermore, intersectional approaches, as discussed by Ahmed and Hammarstedt (2021) and Marlow et al. (2018), reveal how the intersection of identities, including sexuality and gender, shapes the experiences of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs. Through the concept of intersectionality, researchers like Essers and Benschop (2009) illustrate that LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs often engage in identity work to navigate societal expectations and power dynamics that are highly gendered and heteronormative. By offering safe, inclusive spaces for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs, these events empower them to challenge and redefine entrepreneurial norms, paving the way for a more diverse and equitable business landscape.

The Strategic Importance of Trade Exhibitions in Empowering LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurs

Trade exhibitions play an increasingly essential role in empowering LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs, providing a structured and impactful platform for visibility, networking, and resource acquisition in a market often shaped by systemic challenges and exclusion. Events such as #WebSummit #Lisbon 2024 exemplify the integration of diversity initiatives, where the focus on inclusivity within technology and innovation sectors facilitates critical interactions between LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs, investors, and industry leaders. This creates not only opportunities for knowledge exchange but also for forming alliances that might otherwise remain inaccessible in traditional business ecosystems (Gerson, 2022).

At IFEMA Madrid, events like #FITUR (the International Tourism Trade Fair) demonstrate how targeted inclusivity initiatives within the tourism sector can expand market opportunities for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs. FITUR's focus on global networking and cross-cultural partnerships allows entrepreneurs to gain international visibility, particularly important in tourism—a sector where authenticity and inclusivity are increasingly prized by global consumers. By providing a structured environment for knowledge-sharing and

business matchmaking, such exhibitions strengthen LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs' capacities to penetrate new markets and establish their enterprises as viable, competitive entities

The significance of these platforms for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs extends beyond networking. According to recent studies, LGBTQ+ professionals often face isolation and limited access to funding and professional support, underscoring the need for curated events that prioritize inclusive policies (Skrubbe, 2016). Conferences like the #NLGCC International Business & Leadership Conference, #StartOut chapter events, and #Out Leadership Summit create essential forums where LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs engage in skill-building sessions, mentorship, and business-to-business matchmaking—activities critical for their professional development and long-term business sustainability (Gerson, 2022).

Such exhibitions and conferences also serve a vital role in advocating for systemic change within industries and their performative role in the global political economy (Gibson, 2023). By bringing LGBTQ+ entrepreneurship into mainstream business events, trade exhibitions validate the economic and cultural contributions of these entrepreneurs, highlighting their role in driving innovation and resilience. Furthermore, the presence of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurship initiatives within large-scale, international events supports policy efforts toward inclusivity, positioning these exhibitions as catalysts for broader institutional support, as seen in the policy advancements facilitated by trade events in regions like the Netherlands and Germany, where inclusive frameworks bolster economic opportunities for LGBTQ+ communities (Yamamura et al., 2022).

Through their structured platforms and commitment to inclusivity, trade exhibitions not only elevate the profiles of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs but also reinforce the importance of diversity as a strategic asset. These events foster a more equitable business ecosystem, reinforcing the critical role of trade exhibitions in the economic empowerment and visibility of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs and their contributions to global innovation.

Conclusion: Investing in LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurs for a Resilient and Inclusive Economy

LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs bring transformative potential to the economy through resilience, innovation, and diverse perspectives. However, unlocking this potential requires intentional support from investors and policymakers to help them overcome unique challenges rooted in identity and access (Galloway, 2007; Ahmed & Hammarstedt, 2021). Inclusive trade exhibitions and diversity-focused events are vital, providing visibility and supportive networks that empower LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs to thrive and reshape traditional business norms (Wilson, Year; Rumens & Ozturk, 2019).

Cavalcanti et al. (2024) highlight that LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs often exhibit stronger entrepreneurial intentions than their counterparts in traditional markets, driven by unique social motivations and resilience developed through overcoming societal barriers, positioning LGBTQ+ ventures as distinct and impactful contributors to the entrepreneurial landscape.

Moreover, as Morris, Pryor, and Schindehutte (2012) suggest, entrepreneurship is deeply experiential, with each venture-building journey shaping both the entrepreneur and their contributions to the business landscape. Investing in these entrepreneurs is more than a commitment to equity; it is a forward-thinking strategy that strengthens the economy and fosters an inclusive, resilient future for all.

Emphasizing that an individual's agency and career sustainability are influenced by and interconnected with their surrounding context (De Vos et al., 2020), In the context of LGBTQ+ entrepreneurship, an individual's ability to navigate and sustain their entrepreneurial career is deeply shaped by external factors, including cultural norms, legal protections for LGBTQ+ rights, and the visibility of LGBTQ+ communities. Exploring these contextual elements is crucial to understanding how they influence entrepreneurial opportunities, identity expression, and success within the sector.

A diverse and inclusive entrepreneurial landscape is not only equitable but also economically strategic (Hingorani et al., 2022). As (Baboolall & Nee, 2022) McKinsey (2022) concludes, diversity is a proven driver of performance, innovation, and long-term value creation. By investing in LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs and fostering inclusive environments, stakeholders can harness the full potential of underrepresented voices, ensuring that private markets and entrepreneurial ecosystems alike are not just equitable but also positioned for sustained growth and resilience.

Hashtags:

#LGBTQEntrepreneurship #InclusiveEconomy #DiversityInBusiness
#EconomicResilience #EntrepreneurialIdentity #DiversityInvestment #LGBTQFounders
#TradeExhibitions #Innovation #Intersectionality #SupportLGBTQ #PolicyForEquity
#FutureOfBusiness #EmpoweredEntrepreneurs

References:

- Ahmed, A., & Hammarstedt, M. (2022). Customer and worker discrimination against gay and lesbian business owners: a web-based experiment among students in Sweden. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 69(9), 1621-1630.
- Baboolall, D., & Nee, A. (2022). *Tracking diversity, equity, and inclusion data in private markets*. https://www.mckinsey.com/~/_/media/mckinsey/industries/private%20equity%20and%20principal%20investors/our%20insights/tracking%20diversity%20equity%20and%20inclusion%20in%20private%20markets/tracking-diversity-equity-and-inclusion-data-in-private-markets-vf.pdf?shouldIndex=false
- Cavalcanti, A. L., Ferreira, J. J., Mota Veiga, P., Dabic, M., & Meyer, N. (2024). A comparative study of minority entrepreneurship: entrepreneurial intention between LGBT versus traditional markets. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 30(11), 181-204.
- Cha, S. E., Hewlin, P. F., Roberts, L. M., Buckman, B. R., Leroy, H., Steckler, E. L., Ostermeier, K., & Cooper, D. (2019). Being Your True Self at Work: Integrating the Fragmented Research on Authenticity in Organizations. *Academy of Management Annals*, 13(2), 633-671. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2016.0108>
- Chung, Y. B. (1995). Career decision-making difficulties among lesbian, gay, and bisexual individuals. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 42(4), 498-504.
- Collins, A. (2004). Urban Regeneration and the Role of LGBTQ+ Business Clusters. *Urban Studies Journal*.

- De Vos, A., Van der Heijden, B. I., & Akkermans, J. (2020). Sustainable careers: Towards a conceptual model. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 117, 103196.
- Essers, C., van der Heijden, B., Fletcher, L., & Pijpers, R. (2023). It's all about identity: The identity constructions of LGBT entrepreneurs from an intersectionality perspective. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 41(7), 774–795. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02662426221128464>
- Fantappiè, G. (2021). Do LGBTQ+ People Play a Role in Entrepreneurship? A Literature Review and Some Case Studies. Master's Thesis, Politecnico di Milano.
- Fletcher, L., Incerti, V., & Essers, C. (2024a). A social identity perspective on lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) entrepreneurs' networking behavior. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 18(5), 1126–1146.
- Fletcher, L., Incerti, V., & Essers, C. (2024b). A social identity perspective on lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) entrepreneurs' networking behavior. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 18(5), 1126–1146.
- Galloway L (2011) The experiences of male gay business owners in the UK. *International Small Business Journal*. 30(8): 890–906.
- Galloway, L. (2007). Entrepreneurship and the gay minority: why the silence?. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 8(4), 271-280.
- Galloway, L. (2012). Entrepreneurship and Inclusivity: Addressing the Needs of Minority Entrepreneurs. *Journal of Small Business Management*.
- Gerson, E. S. (2022). 10 Events and Conferences for LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurs. Retrieved from HubSpot's Breaking the Blueprint blog series, November 14, 2022.
- Gibson, R. (2023). The Role of International Trade Fairs in the Global Political Economy. In *International Trade Fairs and Inter-Firm Knowledge Flows: Understanding Patterns of Convergence-Divergence in the Technological Specializations of Firms* (pp. 1–21). Springer.
- Hamilton, E. (2013). The discourse of entrepreneurial masculinities (and femininities). *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 25(1–2), 90–99.
- Hingorani, S., Borhaug, M., & Chen, Y. (2022). *The Business Case for Gender Diversity-Beyond Quotas*. <https://www.morganstanley.com/ideas/gender-diversity-investment-management>
- Kidney, E., McAdam, M., & Cooney, T. M. (2024). Everyday prejudices: an intersectional exploration of the experiences of lesbian and gay entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-12-2022-1114>
- Klein, G. (2023a). Transformational and transactional leadership, organizational support and environmental competition intensity as antecedents of intrapreneurial behaviors. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 29(2), 100215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2023.100215>
- Klein, G. (2023b). Transformational and transactional leadership, organizational support and environmental competition intensity as antecedents of intrapreneurial behaviors. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 29(2), 100215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2023.100215>

- Klein, T. (2023). Personal reflections on diversity investment strategies, WebSummit Lisbon.
- Klein, T. (2024, November 13). Day 1 at WebSummit in Lisbon was a whirlwind of energy and insight! [LinkedIn post]. LinkedIn. Retrieved November 14, 2024, from https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tilklein_lisbon-websummit-lgbtqfounders-activity-7262773574019465216-T4xo
- Maldonado-Bautista, I., Klein, P. G., & Artz, K. W. (2023). The Role of Political Values and Ideologies of Entrepreneurs and Financiers. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 47(1), 172-205. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10422587211010496>
- Marlow, S., Giazitzoglu, A., & Down, S. (2018). Heteronormativity and the entrepreneurial self: Discursive constructions of LGBT entrepreneurial identities. *International Small Business Journal*, 36(6), 668-688.
- Morris, M. H., Pryor, C. G., & Schindehutte, M. (2012). *Entrepreneurship as experience: How events create ventures and ventures create entrepreneurs*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Nelson, K. (2023) Diversity in Investment Management: What Are the Latest Trends and Insights?, *Advisor Perspectives*. Available at: <https://www.advisorperspectives.com/commentaries/2023/12/03/diversity-investment-management-latest-trends-and-insights> (Accessed: 14 November 2024).
- Rumens, N., & Ozturk, M. B. (2019). Challenging heteronormativity in entrepreneurial identity: A queer theory approach to the construction of gay male entrepreneurial identities. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 34(6), 671-685.
- Schindehutte, M., Morris, M., & Allen, J. (2005). Homosexuality and entrepreneurship: Implications of gay identity for the venture-creation experience. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 6(1), 27-40.
- Skrubbe, J. S. (2016). *Curating differently: feminisms, exhibitions and curatorial spaces*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Starbuck Gerson, E. (2024) 10 events and conferences for LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs, HubSpot Blog. Available at: <https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/events-and-conferences-for-lgbtq-entrepreneurs> (Accessed: 14 November 2024).
- Washington, M. L., Madden, J. R., Clevenger, M. R., & Miao, C. (2022). The power of entrepreneurs and social systems: Driving forces for empowerment, mitigating disempowerment, and advancing equity. In *Entrepreneurial Communities and Ecosystems* (pp. 100-142). Routledge.
- Wilson, M. (2023). *Queering Entrepreneurship: An Ethnographic Study of a Women-Led Tech Startup in Berlin* (Master's thesis, The University of North Carolina at Charlotte).
- Yamamura, E., & Ozturk, O. (2022). Economic Policies for Inclusive Growth: Lessons from Europe's Support for LGBTQ+ Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*.